

A SYSTEMATIC RESEARCH REVIEW ON TEACHERS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

Teaching profession is a greatest noblest occupation and quality of teachers determines the standard of student performance, success, achievement, etc. As educators one should be always ready for challenges and changes to upgrade skills and knowledge, can be made possible only through continuous Professional Development (PD) and he/she meeting the requisite qualification but lacks skills and no opportunity to update knowledge base cannot be called a qualified or trained teacher. A qualified teacher should be consistently evolving for better performance and appraisal. In this article we will be discussing about the different areas where teacher educators can enhance their professional competencies in order to transact quality education to learners and how improperly qualified educators affect the 21st century educational system.

Key Words: Challenges, Quality, Professional Development, Review, Students, Teachers

Introduction:

Children have the right to quality education without any limitations, it can only be achieved through qualified and trained teachers and in recent time, steps to professionally develop teachers have taken a drastic change. Learners not only benefit from teachers who are qualified and experienced but also those who are constantly upgrading their knowledge base. In order to update the teachers, need programs which will enrich teachers and also enhance their professional competencies. Even if teaching profession has teachers with the required qualifications and experience but no opportunities to upgrade knowledge and skills with changing times and growing needs then it will affect learners' performance adversely. He/she will be termed as improperly qualified teachers. It is a known fact that learning is a lifelong process and so it is imperative for educators to upgrade and continuously participate in professional development programs, in order to benefit the teachers to their roles, a sound professional training is needed. It is through these trainings that teachers get to upgrade their professional skills. A qualified teacher is not only someone who meets the requisite qualifications but also one who is well equipped with technology and at par with the recent trends and he/she who, one is encouraged to grow and develop and nurture oneself as a professional development resource not only to the school but also to the 21st century community.

Objectives:

- Concept of professional development and teacher role
- Professional development of teacher educators and its imbalance
- Challenges and suggestions towards 21st century teacher educator quality

Methodology:

The present study is mainly concentrated on textual approach, articles, papers written on various national and international journals has been considered to do the framework of the study and secondary data has been used.

Professional Development:

It is gaining new skills through continuing education and career training after entering the workforce and can include taking classes or workshops, attending professional or industry conferences, or earning a certificate to expand your knowledge in your chosen field. Professional development is important because it has the potential to open opportunities for career advancement, such as promotions. It can assist you in honing existing skills and in learning new ones. It can also help to stand out in a pool of applicants; showing that to have completed professional development programs/additional industry certifications on your resume can go a long way in showing your expertise in your field. Employees who show initiative in independent learning can signal to employers that you are open to new experiences and are enthusiastic about continuing to grow. It is the continuous process of self-awareness, application, and reflection on how to best apply to strengths and skills to the world of work, Professional development is the set of tools, resources, and training sessions for educators to improve their teaching quality and effectiveness. These resources allow instructors to further their knowledge in their subject area and allows for mentorship and the opportunity to learn new teaching techniques. Those who take part in

workshops/leadership sessions develop and enhance 21st century specialized skills including technical, quantitative and analytical skills. It refers to instructors developing and improving their skills to better meet the needs of their students and approaches to professional development include reviewing case studies, consultation and coaching, mentoring and technical assistance. Here, collaboration and evaluation take place to enable educators to enhance 21st century students' outcomes and some examples of PD activities include, taking courses, seminars, workshops, or retreats, participating in conferences, reading professional journals, magazines, and books, conducting classroom-based research, observing and working with peers, keeping a journal or action plan for development, experimenting with new resources and ideas in the classroom, independently researching educational best practices, etc. and it can help teachers by stay current with best practices, adapt to changing student, family, and community needs, be informed about policies and statutes that govern their work, build to evolving professional responsibilities, boost student outcomes, update their resume with new skills and certifications.

Professional Development: Teacher Educator

The responsibility of preparing qualified and competent teachers rest primarily with teacher education programs, thus positioning teacher educators as "the linchpins in educational reforms of all kinds" (Cochran-Smith, 2003) and the requirement of preparing future teachers for the 21st century heightens the need for teacher educators to be involved in continuous learning through ongoing effective professional development. Professional development of teacher educators has emerged as a key concern in teacher education. The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has emphasized on making teacher education more professional so that teachers are produced with professional outlook and work ethics. But in order to achieve that, teacher educators must become professionals first, Steyn and Niekerk (2002) says PD is an ongoing development program that focuses on the whole range of knowledge, skills and attitudes required to educate learners effectively. Gulston explains that professional development stress the participation of educators or educational leaders in development opportunities in order for them to be better equipped with knowledge and skills. Teachers need to keep up with the global changes, especially in this era where teaching learning has become digital and blended mode and must accommodate all new developments in educational technology, human needs, requirements and creating relevant curriculum appropriate from the enormous range of materials available. The way society functions will keep changing and altering and there will be greater recognition of moral and personal education in a world of pluralistic values and goals, these will affect the way 21st century teachers are educated and trained.

Teacher Education: Imbalance

Teacher Education in India is plagued with imbalances and mismatch, is a huge variation in states and union territories with respect to teachers' qualifications at different levels of educational recruitment procedures and conditions of service. Other variations in parity and cadres of teachers and teacher educators can be seen. These differences are bound to happen in a large system of education in a country like India. Depending on the geographical area and access to education, qualification of teacher educators is also relaxed which leads to improperly qualified teacher educators. With the mushrooming of teacher education institutes in India, the quality of teacher education has degraded gradually and educators are appointed for the sake of it. Quantity is preferred over quality and educators are not appointed on the basis of qualification or experience. Anybody cannot become an educator. With the recent change in the pattern of education system all over the world due to covid-19, the teaching learning approach/ method has shifted to online and blended mode. But how well trained and equipped are educators with technology remains debatable. In order to curb the imbalances, NCTE should come up with reforms and improvised methods of assessment and evaluation for 21st century teacher education institutes.

Professional Development of Teachers: Challenges:

- A teacher should always be willing to adapt and change with the demanding circumstances and situations.
- Sometimes teacher educators are so comfortable with the little knowledge they acquire, they are not willing to upgrade/take up challenges to broaden or expand their skills and knowledge.
- Some teacher educators still use the traditional method of teaching and old age assessment methods which is not at par with the current situation of online and blended mode of teaching and learning.
- Majority stand-alone teacher education institutes are selling degrees for a price and not producing quality teachers.
- They are a hindrance to quality of education.
- Regulatory efforts have not been able to curb the malpractices in the system nor enforce basic standards for quality.
- The methods of teaching should be integrated with ICT knowledge based but teacher educators are neutral towards technology-based teaching.
- The/she are not willing to accommodate innovative teaching strategies and experimental teaching.
- Sufficient time period is not allotted for internship/ practice teaching which hinder the teaching skills of prospective teachers.
- He/she are not willing to undertake research and projects because it is not required and are satisfied with the very little achievement they have acquired.

- Due to the rise in teacher education institutes, there is stagnation in qualifications of teachers and as mentioned quantity is preferred over quality.
- He/she not willing to undergo professional development programmes and even institutes are not encouraging enough to undertake or organise such programmes.
- Unqualified teacher educators are produced because the curriculum of teacher education is purely theoretical and there is not abundant scope to improve teaching skills.
- Teacher education institutes are not producing professional and trained teachers because the concept of teacher education is purely training concept and not practical.

Improvements of Quality of Teacher Educators Towards PD:

- Government should make sure that proper guidelines are followed by teacher education institutes to be deemed for grading so that underperforming institutes can improvised/their recognition be cancelled.
- Quality of teacher education depends solely on the quality of teacher educators.
- Government should plan out to assess and improve the competence of teacher educators by conducting seminars, workshops, conference and inviting articles/papers for publications.
- Enable to identify good teacher educators.
- New approaches in terms of content learning can be enhanced through Massive Open Online Courses.
- It is an open-ended education programme which is broadcasted through the internet and caters to a massive audience and can accommodate a large number of teachers serving in different areas.
- A series of workshop innovatively designed can help identify teacher educators who possess professional skills, which can disseminate through a series of workshop trainings.
- Research in education is not entitled for research scholars only.
- Teacher educators should be encouraged to take up action research on various problems faced by students.
- It is important to consider these differences and provide them with autonomy to choose a professional development programme suitable and beneficial for them.
- He/she be trained to teach a concept together in teams with trans-disciplinary approach.
- Help in making teaching interesting and expertise of all teachers can be put to use together.
- Maintaining academic uniformity in curriculum, structure and duration of the programme can change the scenario of teacher education.
- If uniformity is maintained then teacher education institutes will be able to produce well qualified and trained teachers.

Conclusion:

To be a qualified teacher educator, one should not only possess the required qualifications but also pedagogical skills and knowledge. Learning is a lifelong and continuous process in the same way professional development of teachers should be continuous and engaging. Professional development programs help teachers to enhance professional skills and qualify them to teach in any level of school. The profession of teachers is considered as a noble job and therefore teachers, have to live up to the true profession of teaching. To develop high quality teachers, strategies may differ from one nation to another but when it comes to teacher education there is one common ground and that is the professional development of teacher educators. Many policies and recommendations were made to improve the quality of education but we are yet to see the light of it. NEP 2020 under teacher education also suggests that in order to improve and reach the levels of integrity and credibility required to restore the prestige of teaching profession, the regulatory system shall be empowered to take stringent action against substandard and dysfunctional teacher education institutions that do not meet the basic educational criteria., after giving one year for remedy of breaches and teachers need to continuously enhance their competencies and professional performance. Efforts should be made to actualize mobility of teacher educators across the various stages of education. NCTE is focussed on regulation of teacher education but the focus needs to shift to quality enhancement.

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